

The Functions of Local Media in Local Governance

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Abstract

Local area is faced with various problems. Actors with a variety of skills and expertise are tackling these problems. They are also organizing borderless collaborations and cooperation. This paper proposes a new media category "local media" which help efforts in local governance in three aspects: providing information, resource procurement, facilitating collaborations. Local media have a role that link actors to their supporters and collaborators. This paper formulates these two concepts as a pair-concept, thereby it proposes a new point of view of socio-informatics which has been combining perspectives of social and information science. This proposal is a byproduct of a socio-informatics' encounter with governance theory.

1. Research Background and Purpose

Regional communities in Mongolia are currently facing various problems including depopulation, a decline of various local industries, and the resulting disparities between urban and rural areas. The regional government bodies are financially squeezed, while social and personal networks such as those involving medical care, welfare, and education often fail to meet their intended objectives. Thus, "regional impoverishment" is now underway. While so much has been talked about "regional revitalization," this term belies the extremely difficult challenges confronting regional communities. Under these circumstances, local media are expected to play an important role in the revitalization of regional communities. Local media provide information to the regional community, rather than to the entire nation. They range from newspapers and broadcasters at the prefectural level to newspapers serving cities, towns, villages, and communities that are even smaller.

For the local media, the emphasis is on the creation and maintenance of social and cultural identity of the local community through the documentation and transmission of local traditions and culture, as well as their journalistic functions of reporting on various issues in the community and serving as a mediator between the views of those in urban and regional areas. One of the roles of local media is to work with the local residents and nonprofit organizations to find ways to solve problems through collaboration and cooperation. It is extremely important from the viewpoint of local governance to have a structure in which not only the government but also various actors in the private sector work together to address local problems.

This article, as a point of contact between governance theory and social informatics, focuses on the media's contributions to the efforts to solve various problems of regional

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communities. The article first discusses the author's understanding of governance in connection with the issues addressed herein, and then the role of media in contributing to the development of governance. It further examines the implication of the discussion from the perspective of social informatics, while considering the potential for local media.

2 . Governance Failure and Meta-Governance

Governance, a concept that first emerged in the context of political science, is an empirical and theoretical concept on governing, based on the various political and social actors, or their interrelationships, that form the basis for the value creation and decision-making of institutions (Dowding et al. 2007; Kooiman and Vliet 2000). Evidently, guidelines are crucial to mitigate failures in the pursuit of effective forms of governance. For example, the concept of the "core executive" (Bevir and Rhodes 2003, 56-60); in the theory of meta-governance, assumes the role of the government as being responsible for governance (Jessop 2009); similar to the theory of regulation network, which states that any entity with governing ability other than a political body, can take charge of governance (Sørensen and Torfing 2007, 11-12, 170-175).

However, in these theories, if the existence of a political body is presumed to be a meta-governor, a financial entity, or human resource, it must be regulated in regions where the population is aging and declining. Additionally, it is necessary to address how the functioning of this political body is to be maintained. Communication between individuals and groups as non-governmental actors is disrupted, due to the lack of accurate data in studies involving them. It also indicates that horizontal coordinations are incompatible because of the fragmentation of relationship stability (Meuleman 2008). Furthermore, it takes a long time to negotiate with the various actors involved, since there could be failure in the interactions, a lack of trust between the actors, and the inability to reach a consensus owing to conflicts. However, several studies in recent years have discussed the various cases of consensus building and decision-making failures (Emerson et al. 2012).

These studies indicate the need to redefine the framework for reflexive self-organization that supports the decision-making of the institutions (Jessop 2009). Therefore, this study presents the possibility of empirically analyzing the approach to a meta-governance theory based on the regional theory in the anthropology studies, which provides a background on regulating the actions of the actors involved.

The functions of the metagovernance approach include the following: (1) In terms of decision making, metagovernance are based on a reflexive rationality. It is opposed to the substantial rationality that governs imperative state regulation and the economic rationality that governs competitive market regulation (Sørensen and Torfing 2007 pp.11-12). (2) The metagovernor interacts directly with the other actors participating in governance, encouraging them to communicate and act actively and effectively. This is called "hands-on" coordination. (3) The metagovernor reviews the governance structure and makes changes to the roles of actors when other actors needs to do so. This is called "hands-off" coordination (Sørensen and Torfing 2007 pp.170-175).

3. Supporting Role of Local Media

Problems emerge in local governance when the issues to be addressed and the way in which various actors collaborate with one another become more diverse and fluid. Overcoming such challenges

requires a supporting mechanism. This article examines the role of media as they provide such a mechanism. The article calls such media as “local media” in the sense that they support local governance.

What follows is a discussion on the major supporting functions of local media. One of the challenges involving local governance is the establishment of a shared agenda regarding the issues to be addressed (i.e., targets to be achieved) and the opportunities to be created as a means of making people aware of such issues and opportunities. Local media’s endeavor to tackle various issues in the community will be called “information provision” in this article. Information provision calls attention to certain social issues as they pertain to the local community and promotes efforts to find a solution to such problems. In some cases, mass media such as newspapers and television fulfill this function. In other cases, social media fulfill this function by sharing and spreading information. An example of the latter would be FixMyStreet, an online platform that reports on community problems. FixMyStreet allows ordinary citizens to report on road damage, graffiti, illegal dumping, and so on to be communicated to the local government for action.

Next challenge involving local governance relates to the gathering of necessary resources and supplies for daily activities. Local media serve as a bridge between those seeking assistance and those offering necessary support. One example of local media that specialize in fulfilling this resource procurement function would be crowdfunding sites.

Another challenge in regard to which local media can help relates to initiatives that any single individual actor cannot adequately achieve; local media can establish horizontal relationships among various actors. Local media are called upon to serve as an intermediary among various actors to establish such collaborative relationships and facilitating collaboration. An interesting case in this regard would be online campaign platforms that have emerged in recent years. For example, Causes is used by individuals and group leaders to recruit other individuals and groups to collaborate with them. It allows leaders to collect signatures for pledges of support, petitions, and so on. Organizations recognized as nonprofits under the U.S. laws—those that can receive tax benefits—can raise funds through this platform.

The above discussion is based on the three functions of local media as organized by the author. In light of the specific examples of local media, it can be observed that most media outlets serve more than one of these functions simultaneously. For instance, websites that report on community issues provide information while connecting the actors raising the issues (citizens) and those responding to the issues (municipalities).

Meanwhile, funding sites help actors raise funds while at the same time serving as a bridge between actors seeking funds and those committed to donations. Online campaign platforms simultaneously provide information regarding the initiatives pursued by leaders, help raise resources for their activities, and facilitate collaboration among actors. As is clear from the above discussion, information provision is an important aspect of the functions of local media. However, local media also play a role that is more complex than this aspect. Local media mediate information, while also mediating collaboration and cooperation among actors participating in local governance. This view of the media highlights the functions that they could perform with respect to local governance. Under this view, media outlets that have been classified into traditional categories, such as mass media and social media, could also be called “local media” depending on their functions.

4. The Functions of Local Media as a Meta-governor

In this paper, we pair the functions that a meta-governor would need with those that local media would need. To examine meta-governance theory's empirical applicability, we reviewed newspapers published by hometown association of Arkhangai province in Mongolia.

Figure 1. The newspapers published by hometown association of Arkhangai

One of the characteristics of meta-governance theory is the emphasis on actors' "reflexive rationality". Consequently, we needed information that matched each actor's aims and background. For example, newspapers published by hometown association provide information to encourage reflexivity regarding their home town. Empirical studies have shown that people often support and engage in problem-solving activities in their current or former home towns (Matsaganis 2011, Bolormaa 2017).

Another characteristic of meta-governance theory is the function of "hands-on" coordination, which facilitates interaction among actors. Local media are able to promote projects that individual actors cannot fully promote, and stimulate interaction among actors, as well as collaboration and cooperation among multiple actors. For example, hometown association can

encourage collaboration among members by hosting special or annual events. We hypothesize that collaboration between former residents and current residents, as well as between current residents and local firms, would continue as a result.

The third characteristics of meta-governance theory is the impact of a person who is not directly involved with the actors participating in governance, but who is merely an external observer. Coordinations are made when necessary by reviewing existing governance structures and changing actors' roles. This is called "hands-off" coordination. At a local level, activities are initiated by local residents, public bodies, such as local agricultural co-ops and tourist boards, and firms that have deep roots in the locality, such as established local firms. Hometown association procure resources by selecting other firms and individuals and allocate roles where necessary to achieve a specific goal when local activities need to be maintained.

Consequently, local media do not only provide information but also have the potential to serve as a meta-governor by working with hometown association to solve local problems.

5. Conclusion

Contemporary society faces a number of problems, both locally and globally. Actors with diverse skills and expertise engage in problem-solving activities through borderless collaboration and cooperation with diverse levels of commitment. This study examines such contemporary activities with reference to the concept of local governance, and proposes the concept of local media as a category of support for local governance.

Social informatics has two foci that form an ellipse: "society" and "information." The two foci can be integrated into a single perspective on problems related to social informatics by focusing on "the work of information in a social context" and "the work of media reporting on it."

Earlier studies in social informatics are diverse and contain many attempts to address the various challenges faced by local communities and to identify potential solutions. This study constructs a comprehensive framework to understand research practices in social informatics to provide an academic contribution to governance, by focusing on studies on social informatics and the theory of governance. The study also examines potential synergy between social informatics and theory of governance.

However, the discussion in this study only shows the theoretical framework of governance and the functions of local media. Several issues need to be addressed in the empirical analysis, including the conditions of each function and the operation of hometown association.

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